

The Expression of Goodness and Evil in English and Uzbek Phraseological Units

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 28 May2025; **Accepted:**28 Jun2025; **Published:**31Jul2025

Introduction. Phraseological units reflect the historical, cultural, ethical, and intellectual worldview of a people. Specifically, the phraseological application of axiological lexemes such as “*yaxshi*” (*good*) and “*yomon*” (*bad*) illustrates how cultures conceptualize moral virtue and vice. In both English and Uzbek, the idiomatic representation of these values necessitates a comparative-pragmatic and linguocultural approach in linguistic research. Significant theoretical contributions to the study of national phraseological features have been made by numerous scholars. Notably, N.N. Amosova emphasized contextual relationships in idioms, while A.V. Kunin proposed their classification based on linguocultural criteria. Additionally, Cowie’s analytical works on English phraseology, as well as the theoretical perspectives of Telia and Rahmatullaev, form the methodological basis of this study. The idiomatic expression of axial concepts like “good” and “bad” should also be analyzed within the frameworks of axial semantics and axiological linguistics.

As Telia states, the value system encoded in language serves as a verbal reflection of a nation's cultural archetypes.

Methodology. This study analyzes phraseological units through semantic, pragmatic, and linguocultural lenses. Idioms containing the English lexemes “*good*” and “*bad*,” and their Uzbek equivalents “*yaxshi*” and “*yomon*,” were selected. The corpus includes modern English and Uzbek literature, dictionaries, collections of idioms, and scholarly sources. Data were drawn from the Oxford Dictionary of Idioms, O‘zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug‘ati (Explanatory Phraseological Dictionary of Uzbek), and literary texts. Selected idioms contain “*good/bad*” or “*yaxshi/yomon*” and represent emotional, evaluative, ironic, or colloquial expressions. Using a comparative approach, the study evaluates the axiological (moral) significance of each idiom and analyzes their communicative-pragmatic roles. Special attention is given to their connotative and cultural meanings.

Results. The following tables compare English and Uzbek idioms involving “good/bad” and “yaxshi/yomon,” based on semantic, connotative, and pragmatic criteria.

Table 1.

English idioms containing “good” and “bad”

No	Idiom	Meaning	Pragmatic Remark
1	A good deal	A large amount or degree	Emphasizes quantity; informal and widely used.
2	As good as gold	A very well-	Positive character

		behaved child	assessment; positive connotation.
3	A good egg	A reliable, good person	Carries warmth and sincerity.
4	Bad blood	Hostility, resentment	Expresses negative relationships; emotionally charged.
5	Go bad	To spoil, go rotten (food)	Literal meaning, also used metaphorically.
6	A bad apple	A bad person with negative influence	Metaphor for someone who causes group deterioration.

Table 2.***Uzbek idioms containing “yaxshi” and “yomon”***

№	Idiom	Meaning	Contextual Usage
1	Yaxshi niyat – yarim davlat	Good intentions are half of success	Yaxshi niyat – yarim davlat, deb har ishni bismilloh bilan boshladi.
2	Yaxshi odam / inson	A respectable, honorable person	Uni qishloqda hamma yaxshi odam deb biladi.
3	Do‘st yomon kunda bilinadi	A true friend is known in hardship	Qiyin damlarda u yonimdan ketmadi – do‘st yomon kunda bilinadi.
4	Yomon gap tarqamasin	Let negative talk not spread	Bu haqida hech kimga gapirib yurma, yomon gap tarqamasin.
5	Yomon niyat qilma	Do not harbor ill intentions	Doimo yomon niyat qilasan, sizning ham og‘zingizdan yaxshi so‘z chiqadimi?
6	Yaxshi qiz mahalladan ortmaydi	A well-raised girl doesn't wander far from home	Onam aytgan: yaxshi qiz mahalladan ortmaydi.

Discussion. V.V. Telia links the axiological nature of phraseological units to their cultural connotations, asserting that concepts such as “good” and “bad” are deeply intertwined with societal values. A.V. Kunin regards phraseological units as markers of national-cultural identity, describing them as a “linguistic model of national culture.” His classification suggests that these idioms perform evaluative, ironic, and emotionally expressive functions.

Sh. Rahmatullaev emphasizes the role of “yaxshi” and “yomon” components in expressing moral and ethical norms within folk creativity. Cowie’s work focuses on the structural stability, complexity, and semantic integrity of idioms, exploring their place in the lexico-semantic system. According to Amosova’s contextual phraseology, each idiom has a distinct “semantic core within discourse.” For instance, “a bad egg” often refers to an untrustworthy person but may also evoke reluctant sympathy, while “yomonning telpagi qozondek” suggests that wrongdoing leaves a lasting negative imprint on one’s reputation, reflecting a cultural warning against immoral actions.

Conclusion. The comparative analysis demonstrates that idioms containing “yaxshi”/“good” and “yomon”/“bad” encapsulate core moral-aesthetic values inherent in Uzbek and English linguistic and cultural systems. These phraseological units perform functions such as moral judgment, regulation of social behavior, and conveyance of irony or social commentary, thus serving as both linguistic expressions and cultural indicators. This study has significant implications for foreign language pedagogy in conveying the cultural nuances of idioms, for translation studies in resolving equivalence issues, and for linguistics research in axiological semantics.

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